

DIGITAL EDUCATION: NEW DIRECTIONS IN TRANSFORMING THE EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN

Elmurodov Jamshid Asatullayevich

*Associate Professor of “Mathematics and Information
Technologies” Department at Oriental University
ergashevmuhammadsodiq1995@gmail.com
+998(97)440-01-64*

Abstract. This article discusses fundamental reforms in education, the importance of digitalization of the education system, electronic platforms, advantages of digitalization in improving education quality and monitoring, continuous professional platforms, giant electronic platforms and their conveniences, digitalization in general secondary and higher education systems, and the importance of learning in the digital world. MOOC (MOOC - massive open distance education system).

Keywords: electronic books, electronic textbooks, digital interactive teaching aids, distance education, digital technology, digitalization, “EDU LINK” information system, HEMIS program, electronic platforms, innovative platforms, online platforms, digital economy, digital platforms, digital transformation, “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030”, robotics, artificial intelligence, “super platforms”.

INTRODUCTION. In today's rapidly developing world, modern information technologies and computer capabilities have penetrated all sectors. In particular, modern technologies play an invaluable role in the educational process. Fundamental reforms in the education system are aimed at making a breakthrough in building a “New Uzbekistan” using modern technologies. The goal is to digitalize the education system, establish distance learning, create electronic platforms and use them to improve education quality, eliminate corruption, and create conveniences in education. Particularly, the Presidential Decree No. PF 6079 dated October 5, 2020, “On approval of the Digital Uzbekistan-2030 strategy and measures for its implementation” focused on improving the digitalization process in the digital world

and set specific goals.[3]

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS. The main purpose of adopting various decrees, resolutions, and laws regarding fundamental changes in education in our country is aimed at improving the country's economy, living standards, and production processes. This process can be achieved through fundamental reform of education, training competitive qualified personnel, and achieving a worthy position in international assessment ratings.[4] During the global pandemic, the shortcomings in our digital education process became clearly visible. In this regard, there were many gaps, especially in higher education institutions and general education schools, which proved our above statement.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis, it was specifically emphasized that digital knowledge and modern information technologies must be mastered to achieve development, that this provides an opportunity to take the shortest path to growth, and that today enterprises are completely far from digital technologies.[1] It was explained that digital technologies not only improve the quality of products and services but also reduce excess costs, increase efficiency, and in short, can dramatically improve people's lives.

Tasks were set to develop and implement the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” program, which envisages updating all sectors of the economy based on digital technologies. This creates even wider opportunities for modernizing leading industries and strengthening competitiveness, introducing advanced technologies, establishing high-tech enterprises, technology parks, production enterprises, and creating modern engineering and communication infrastructures. When observing foreign experience in improving technological knowledge in education, it can be seen that industry and social spheres have been developed through technological knowledge.

Since the early 2000s, Uzbekistan began giving priority to the development of information and communication technologies (ICT) and digitalization[6]. In particular, the “Comprehensive Program for the Development of the National

Information and Communication System of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2013-2020”[5], “Action Strategy on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021”[2], and “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” and “Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026” provide for a number of measures aimed at implementing digital transformation in the national economy, industry, and society as a whole.

In particular, after the launch of the main system of our country’s e-government - the Single Interactive State Services Portal (my.gov.uz), significant achievements were made in this field, as well as in the introduction of new technologies and digitalization in public administration. As a result, as of January 2022, 56 percent of state services were provided through my.gov.uz, the number of state services on this e-government platform reached 307, and more than 1.3 million citizens used e-government services. At the same time, the total number of Internet users in Uzbekistan reached 27.2 million at the beginning of this year.

In addition, during the past period, large investments were attracted to the sector to improve the ICT systems and digital infrastructure of the republic. As a result, according to the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the gross value added in the information and communication sector more than doubled in 2017-2021, reaching 11.8 trillion soums (more than 1 billion US dollars) in 2021.

Also, since the establishment of IT parks in Uzbekistan, exports in the sector have increased 50 times and reached 46 million US dollars. The number of permanent residents of the park increased from 147 to 500, more than 300 new companies were opened, and 8,500 high-paying jobs were created. Currently, more than 11,000 young people work in IT parks. The “One Million Uzbek Programmers” project is designed for free distance learning for the population of Uzbekistan over 12 years old. The main goal of the project is to train a new generation of specialists with programming skills in the field of digital technologies. “One Million Uzbek Coders” are online courses where each student independently studies materials, completes assignments and laboratory work on the uzbekcoders.uz platform.

Project goal: Implementation of Udacity platform distance learning

methodology in schools within the framework of the “One Million Uzbek Coders” project. Learning Management Systems (LMS) are online platforms that organize and implement e-learning programs and provide the ability to monitor and store student performance results. “Las Virtual” platforms are technological tools or computer applications specifically designed to serve as support in educational contexts, facilitating interaction, content access, and consultation at different times and places, synchronously and asynchronously when needed.

The total length of fiber-optic communication lines in our country has grown significantly since 2017. For example, according to the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this indicator increased almost 6 times in 2017-2022, reaching a total length of 118 thousand kilometers of fiber-optic communication lines in January 2022. Also, since 2017, the bandwidth of the international data transmission network has increased 28 times, from 64.2 Gbps to 1800 Gbps.

It should be noted that the global pandemic showed the need for digitalization and digital transformation, and Uzbekistan's digitalization strategy was reviewed and improved to address urgent issues in the IT field and ensure sustainable development.

CONCLUSION.

The advantages of digitalization and electronic platforms in education include:

- Ensuring transparency and openness of higher education institutions;
- Automation of educational, scientific, administrative, and financial processes in higher education;
- Prevention of bureaucratic barriers and reduction of financial costs in higher education;
- Ensuring continuity between higher education institutions, students, and employing organizations;
- Reducing time spent on management processes and increasing labor efficiency;

- Monitoring the effectiveness of educational process participants;
- Formation of analytical data and optimization and acceleration of decision-making process;
- Ensuring strong integration of modern digital technologies and educational technologies, creating additional conditions for continuous development of teachers' professional skills;
- Individualization of educational processes based on digitalization;
- Creating a system for placing information about educational-methodical complexes by subjects using QR-codes for downloading and transferring electronic educational literature on technological education to mobile devices;
- Organization of distance education programs based on modern information and communication technologies;
- Use of platforms (such as Hemis, Moodle) that allow online monitoring and mastering of theoretical and practical classes, as well as downloading them to electronic information storage devices, and use of innovative technologies in educational processes;
- Expanding opportunities for using electronic library systems that allow remote access and placing educational-methodical complexes and electronic educational resources developed for the technological education system;
- Development of the use of modern software products widely used internationally in the educational process, based on the specifics of technological education. Uzbekistan aims to take a firm place among strong democratic, advanced developed countries. The main task is to enter the top 50 developed countries in the world. Reforms in this direction are being implemented to create decent conditions for our people.

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